

**Navigating Society's Turmoil: Anjum's Identity Struggle in Arundhati
Roy's *The Ministry of Utmost Happiness***

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Abstract:

Arundhati Roy's novel The Ministry of Utmost Happiness presents a rich tapestry of characters and themes, prominently featuring Anjum, a transgender woman whose journey serves as a poignant exploration of societal norms and personal identity in contemporary India. This research article delves into Anjum's struggle with societal expectations and her quest for self-discovery, analyzing how Roy navigates complex themes of gender, religion, and marginalization through Anjum's narrative arc. Drawing upon critical analysis and close reading of the text, this article seeks to elucidate the nuances of Anjum's character, examining the ways in which she challenges conventional notions of identity and belonging while negotiating the intersections of gender, religion, and socio-political dynamics in Indian society.

Keywords: Gender identity, Societal norms, Marginalization, Negotiation, Transgender, Identity, Cultural norms, self-perception.

Introduction:

Arundhati Roy's *The Ministry of Utmost Happiness* is a literary masterpiece that immerses readers in the intricacies of contemporary India, offering a mosaic of characters and narratives that reflect the diverse fabric of Indian society. At the heart of this novel is Anjum, a transgender woman whose journey unfolds against the backdrop of a complex and ever-changing social landscape. Anjum's struggle with societal expectations and her own identity serves as a compelling lens through which Roy explores themes of gender, religion, and marginalization, inviting readers to confront their assumptions and prejudices while grappling with questions of belonging and acceptance.

They can be traced back to Hindu mythology, where they are frequently venerated as demigods and linked to different deities. In the past, hijras held significant positions in society as entertainers, protectors of fertility, and contributors to crucial rituals like childbirth and marriages. Hijras demonstrate a profound affiliation with celestial beings, particularly deities such as Siva, especially when representing the ardhnanarisvara (a being that is both male and

female), Rama in Ramayana, and Arjuna in Mahabharata. Nevertheless, cultural perceptions about hijras have experienced substantial transformations as time has passed. The presence of esteemed hijras under the Mughal dynasty is evident in this tale.

Hijras in present-day India encounter a multitude of difficulties throughout several domains of their existence. An important challenge they face is societal discrimination and prejudice. They frequently endure familial rejection, suffer obstacles in accessing educational and employment prospects, and confront harassment, assault, and verbal mistreatment in public areas. The discrimination experienced by hijras is based on deeply entrenched societal prejudices, cultural stigmas, and a dearth of comprehension or recognition of multiple gender identities.

The issue of legal recognition and protection for hijras in India has been a topic of continuous discussion and advancement. In 2014, the Supreme Court of India officially acknowledged hijras as a distinct third gender and confirmed their entitlement to constitutional rights and legal safeguards. This pivotal ruling was a notable stride towards inclusiveness and acknowledgment of their individual identities. Nevertheless, the execution and conversion of legal rights into concrete society transformations continue to pose a difficulty.

Hijras also express significant apprehension regarding their access to healthcare and social welfare services. Numerous individuals have challenges in accessing sufficient healthcare as a result of healthcare practitioners' limited understanding and lack of sensitivity towards their particular requirements. Furthermore, those who face socioeconomic risks and have limited opportunities for formal employment frequently experience economic difficulties and are often excluded from social welfare programmes. Nevertheless, both governmental and non-governmental organisations have made concerted efforts to tackle the challenges encountered by hijras in India. Multiple advocacy groups and community-based organisations are actively engaged in empowering hijras, advocating for their rights, offering support services, and promoting awareness and acceptance in society. Furthermore, there are ongoing efforts to enhance the socioeconomic circumstances of these individuals through projects that focus on education, skill enhancement, and entrepreneurship.

Although there is some improvement, the journey towards complete inclusion and acceptance of hijras in Indian culture continues to be arduous. Education, awareness, and policy reforms are essential for establishing an atmosphere that values and commemorates many gender identities. India has the ability to progress towards a more inclusive and fair society that

recognises the rights and dignity of all its inhabitants, irrespective of their gender identity, by embracing the distinctive contributions and experiences of hijras.

Anjum, a character in Arundhati Roy's novel *The Ministry of Utmost Happiness*, represents the intricate and demanding process of negotiating one's identity in a compelling manner. Anjum's struggle with societal and personal challenges takes front stage in the narrative, set amid a dynamic and politically heated Indian society. According to Butler's perspective in 1990, gender should not be seen as something that is simply determined by external factors, but rather as an active process through which we shape our own identities. Roy explores the complexities of Anjum's challenges as she navigates the intersections of gender, religion, sexuality, and society norms, ultimately illuminating the bigger themes of identity, inclusivity, and the pursuit of personal uniqueness.

Anjum, a hijra, embodies a marginalised minority in India that defies conventional gender conventions. During her journey, Roy examines the complexities of identity and the conflicts that develop when an individual's self-perception conflicts with cultural norms. "For over three decades, Anjum resided in the Khwabgah, with her amalgamated physique and her partially fulfilled aspirations." Roy, aged 29. Anjum's experiences exemplify the challenges encountered by nonconformists, shedding light on the intricacies of their existence in a society that frequently overlooks or rejects their true identities.

Moreover, Anjum's struggle against societal norms mirrors the broader socio-political situation in India, a nation wrestling with its own crisis of identity. Roy skillfully integrates the storyline with several historical occurrences, such as the Bhopal gas tragedy and the Kashmir dispute, creating a setting that reflects the unrest and disunity inside the country. Roy presented the book by drawing a comparison between the Delhi community and the Hijra community. Anjum asserts that the novel depicts a household with an uninterrupted history that dates back as far as the deteriorated city itself. 'The walls that are peeling, the roof that is leaking, and the sunlit courtyard were all once magnificent.' Roy is 44 years old. Anjum serves as a symbolic figure, embodying the challenges of establishing one's identity and gaining acknowledgment in a community that is divided by religious, political, and cultural differences.

In addition, the exploration of identity negotiation goes beyond the limitations imposed by society and dives into the personal struggles experienced by Anjum. Roy prompts readers to reflect on the common challenge of self-acceptance and the ongoing balancing act between personal ambitions and cultural norms, as she grapples with her own wishes, uncertainties, and

anxieties. Anjum's journey serves as a profound investigation of the intricacies of human identity and the innate yearning for both acceptance and personal fulfilment.

Gender Negation and Societal Structure:

Anjum's struggle with societal norms and personal conflicts in Arundhati Roy's novel *The Ministry of Utmost Happiness* serves as a prime example of the intricate and demanding process of negotiating one's identity. Roy examines the challenges, contradictions, and changes that people encounter while dealing with cultural norms and wrestling with their own identity through her character. Anjum's transgender identity as a hijra plays a significant role in her debates of identity. Hijras in India hold a marginalised status, as they defy conventional gender standards and confront discrimination and stigmatisation. According to Lakshmi Narayan Tripathi, hijras are a visible sexual minority, but they are often regarded as if they are invisible. I assert that I have never been imperceptible. I perceived myself as an individual apart from the collective, rather than being part of the collective itself. Anjum's path exemplifies the challenges encountered by hijras in Indian society, as she grapples with familial rejection, experiences aggression and mistreatment, and navigates restricted options for school and employment. The confrontation she faces with society illuminates the deeply rooted societal prejudices and cultural stigmas around gender and sexuality.

all things, not just living things but all things – carpets, clothes, books, pens, musical instruments – had a gender. Everything was either masculine or feminine, man or woman. Everything except her baby. Yes of course she knew there was a word for those like him – Hijra. (Roy, 13)

Anjum's mother's contemplation on the gender of her offspring. She acknowledges that hijras have a separate gender identity in South Asia, commonly classified as a third gender. She is unwilling to acknowledge that. This reference emphasises the wide range of gender identities in the region and the overarching topic of not conforming to traditional gender norms in the novel. Furthermore, it raises concerns regarding the societal and legal acknowledgment of these identities, which might be a primary focus in numerous communities. It indirectly criticises the notion that gender is an innate and unchanging attribute. On the contrary, it proposes that gender is a societal creation that is imposed on all aspects of life, highlighting the pervasive influence of gender norms and expectations in society. This is consistent with current debates on the performative aspect of gender. Anjum is an exception in a world that classifies everything as either masculine or feminine. This highlights the recurring theme of seclusion, alienation, and exclusion that pervades the narrative. The infant's identification defies

conventional society conventions and reveals the hardships faced by those who do not conform to existing gender classifications.

The talks that Anjum has with her internal self have equal importance. While exploring her identity, she scrutinises her own desires, ambitions, and comprehension of gender and love. She engages in a process of introspection and self-approval, continuously reevaluating her sense of inclusion and creating her own trajectory in the face of society expectations. She desired to live a conventional life, just like any other human being.

Now she wanted to return to the Duniya and live like an ordinary person. She wanted to be a mother, to wake up in her own home, dress Zainab in a school uniform and send her off to school with her books and tiffin box. (Roy, 30)

Anjum's identity negotiations are significantly influenced by the socio-cultural backdrop of contemporary India portrayed in the novel. The inclusion of historical events, such as the Bhopal gas tragedy and the Kashmir conflict, introduces further intricacies to her challenges. Anjum's path is influenced by societal biases and cultural conventions related to gender, religion, and politics. This emphasises how individual identity struggles are interconnected with wider socio-political forces. Anjum's struggle with society and herself holds a broader importance that goes beyond her own narrative. It prompts inquiries on the level of acceptance within society, inclusiveness, and the influence of power dynamics on the formation of identities. Roy encourages readers to engage in critical introspection over the intricate process of navigating one's identity, questioning conventional concepts of gender and sexuality, and fighting for a society that is more comprehensive and compassionate. *The Ministry of Utmost Happiness* offers a deep examination of the process of negotiating one's identity, as demonstrated via Anjum's struggle with both society and herself. Roy's evocative narrative, intricate character portrayal, and examination of socio-cultural environments converge to form a captivating story that prompts readers to reflect on the intricacies of personal identity, the influence of societal expectations, and the profound ability to embrace oneself in the midst of challenges.

Anjum's journey towards establishing her identity is riddled with hardships and challenges. As a transgender individual, or hijra, in Indian society, Anjum faces deep-rooted prejudice, discrimination, and marginalization. Laxmi Narayan says that “We, hijras, are not hypocrites. We live our sexuality openly, being truthful to our souls and our bodies. Science and doctors assigned something else to us when we were born - which they didn't have the authority to - but we choose what we are and we are very truthful about it.” Anjum's struggles

are emblematic of the larger difficulties experienced by hijras in India and reflect the complexities inherent in negotiating one's identity. One of the central hardships Anjum encounters is the rejection and alienation she faces from her own family. She experiences profound heartache when her parents disown her and refuse to accept her identity. This familial rejection leaves her feeling isolated and sets the stage for her battle with society and self. Anjum's longing for acceptance and belonging becomes a driving force in her search for identity.

Within the novel, the "Khwabgah" (House of Dreams) emerges as Anjum's realm of emancipation and self-expression, signifying her liberation from societal constraints. As a permanent dweller of the Khwabgah, Anjum was at last unburdened, donning the attire she had yearned for (p. 25). Conversely, her dual vocalization in the "Duniya" (World) unsettled others, instilling fear even in governmental figures who dreaded the Hijra's potential curses (p. 28, 67). Anjum's marginalization stemmed from superficial aspects, misinformation, and entrenched myths, prompting her to combat gender hierarchies and accepted norms, aligning her journey with anti-colonial resistance. Enthralled by her emotional impulses, she remained within the Khwabgah for three decades. Her life took a turn when she discovered an abandoned or lost infant girl, Zainab. Anjum brought her into the Khwabgah fold, offering her a name and care. Subsequently, witnessing the aftermath of the Gujrat massacre stemming from the Godhra train attack, Anjum underwent traumatic upheaval, prompting her to leave the Khwabgah. Finding solace in a local graveyard, she transformed it into the "Jannat Guest House," concurrently initiating funeral services for the marginalized and destitute, thereby shaping a sanctuary for societal upliftment

Additionally, Anjum confronts various forms of violence and abuse throughout her life. She endures physical assaults and verbal slurs, which further marginalize and dehumanize her. These experiences highlight the vulnerability and constant threat hijras face in society, leading Anjum to internalize a sense of fear and mistrust. In one part of the novel, Anjum has been prejudiced by the student in music class by saying that, "He's a She. He's not a He or a She. He's a He and a She. She-He, He-She Hee! Hee! Hee!" (Roy, 12). Such hardships expose the systemic oppression that hijras often endure, reflecting the deeply ingrained prejudices within Indian society. Moreover, Anjum's struggle for identity is intensified by the limited access to education, employment, and healthcare that hijras typically face. The novel depicts Anjum's experiences of navigating an unjust social system that denies her basic rights and opportunities.

The lack of resources and support structures further compound her challenges, making her battle for self-discovery and self-acceptance even more arduous.

Anjum's hardships are not limited to external forces but also encompass her internal conflicts and uncertainties. As she grapples with her gender identity and explores her desires, she is confronted with profound questions about love, intimacy, and self-worth. Anjum's journey involves a constant renegotiation of her own understanding of herself and her place in society. These internal struggles demonstrate the complexity of the process of self-discovery and the resilience required to navigate a world that often refuses to acknowledge one's true identity.

Anjum's story serves as a poignant reminder of the countless obstacles that individuals like her face in their pursuit of self-acceptance, belonging, and dignity. The hardships faced by Anjum in *The Ministry of Utmost Happiness* emphasize the profound challenges of identity negotiation for hijras in Indian society. By highlighting these struggles, Arundhati Roy invites readers to confront their own biases and engage in a broader dialogue about the need for inclusivity, acceptance, and social change.

Conclusion

In *The Ministry of Utmost Happiness*, Arundhati Roy offers a profound exploration of Anjum's struggle with society and her own identity, inviting readers to engage with themes of gender, marginalization, and social justice. Through Anjum's character, Roy challenges conventional notions of identity and belonging, urging readers to embrace diversity and empathy in the face of difference. Anjum's journey serves as a testament to the resilience of the human spirit and the enduring quest for dignity and acceptance in a world fraught with inequality and prejudice.

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